

Expanding the Space Biology Community: NASA Open Science Data Repository's Analysis Working Groups

Survey Report

Paola Castaño

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Foreword

Data sharing, curation and mining are widely recognized as vital activities to scientific discovery, particularly when it comes to invaluable datasets such as those generated in biological spaceflight experiments. Yet identifying best practices to disseminate data effectively, responsibly and sustainably remains a challenge. It has been a pleasure and a privilege to learn from the progress made by the Analysis Working Groups (AWGs) instituted by the NASA Open Science Data Repository (OSDR) in exploring, developing and implementing ways to access, interpret, and re-use biological data generated in space.

Within the project “A Philosophy of Open Science for Diverse Research Environments”, the AWGs experience is analyzed alongside that of many other research groups working with biological, environmental and biomedical data around the globe (ranging from Italy to Brazil, Greece, Ghana, the United Kingdom, and India). Our aim is to understand the conditions under which data sharing best contributes to ongoing scientific efforts. A key finding across these case studies is that in the absence of community involvement – in the form of regular consultation and engagement of prospective data users – data sharing initiatives tend to fail. *A key incentive to meaningful data re-use is the ability to provide feedback into the design and governance of data standards and infrastructures.* This makes data amenable to researchers’ specific goals while also enhancing researchers’ understanding of Open Science tools - thereby fostering skills to deploy such tools responsibly and creatively. The AWGs have provided participants with precisely such an opportunity: a venue for direct and regular exchange between data creators, prospective data users, and OSDR developers, through which a wide variety of biologists and space scientists could interact with NASA staff towards building and deploying data infrastructures. As our findings show, such exchange generates more effective pathways towards discovery alongside an expanded community of practice with the power and vision to address some of the most pressing concerns of our time through sustained collaboration and exchange.

These efforts run parallel to the working groups successfully established in the domains of public health, crop science, epidemiology and meteorology - among others - by organizations such as the Research Data Alliance and the many regional Open Science Clouds (for other examples, see <https://opensciencestudies.eu/publications/>). Fostering such community practices is crucial to the development and maintenance of a healthy data ecosystem in the long term, which in turn constitutes an essential condition for resilient and trustworthy AI-powered innovation.

Sabina Leonelli,
February 2025

Executive Summary

This report is an output of the project “A Philosophy of Open Science for Diverse Research Environments” (PHIL_OS) led by Sabina Leonelli, and the case study focused on the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Open Science Data Repository (OSDR) led by Paola Castaño. The case study examines the data processing and sharing practices enabled by OSDR and the role of the Analysis Working Groups (AWGs) bringing together users of the data. The overall goal in this study is to shed light on how open science practices are transforming space biology, and the relationship between the repository’s goals of maximizing discovery and democratizing access.

The AWGs have brought together a broad network of approximately 600 scientists from academia, government, and industry to engage with OSDR datasets. This report presents results from a survey conducted between 2023 and 2024 that aimed to characterize the AWG members, their expertise, and experience participating in the groups. The survey included 30 questions and 70 respondents completed it. 61 of them were not affiliated with NASA at the time of the survey, and the remaining 9 were part of the agency working either as civil servants or contractors.

The following are the two key findings from the survey:

1. The AWGs are expanding the space biology community in four ways. First, they are bringing researchers into the field who were not previously involved with spaceflight research. Second, they are expanding the realms of expertise, skills, and scientific questions that are relevant for space biology. Third, they are including a more diverse range of individuals in terms of their demographic characteristics and career stages. And fourth, they are engaging researchers who already have experience with open science practices outside of space biology.
2. The reported experiences of participation in the AWGs and the respondents’ assessments about several dimensions of OSDR are predominantly favorable and diverse in their aims and modalities. The respondents express positive views about several essential characteristics of the repository and propose courses of action for improvement. The diversity of experiences shows that there is not a single or a primary expected result of participation from the members’ perspectives, but rather sustained interactions among them which lead to different outcomes.

Both findings invite a continuous characterization of the changing space biology scientific community enabled by open science, and pose the challenge of sustaining its growth considering the goals of building a science community in size, diversity of technical expertise, and lived experience. The finding about the expansion of the community invites a more detailed tracing of whether and how the new scientists that participate in the groups remain in the field, and their impact in moving it forward. The finding about the diverse experiences of participation calls for the development of new metrics to assess the groups' work. The program has appropriately emphasized that the AWGs have significantly increased the knowledge generated per experiment, particularly in terms of returns on investment regarding publications. However, what counts as participation and productivity – and open science more broadly - in the groups goes beyond publications, and there are other dimensions of AWG members' interactions and work not currently reflected in those figures.

A continuous and careful examination of the AWGs is important for OSDR to learn about the groups' work, for NASA's move towards open science, and also for global studies about good practices in open science. In the PHIL_OS team we hope this survey report is a first step in this continuous examination.

Introduction

The NASA Open Science Data Repository (OSDR) is an open science program from the Division of Biological and Physical Sciences (BPS), which is part of the agency's Science Mission Directorate (SMD). It is an interactive open-access database, specimen repository, and collaboration space that incorporates the Ames Life Sciences Data Archive (ALSDA), the NASA Biological Institutional Scientific Collection (NBISC), the NASA Space Biology Biospecimen Sharing Program (BSP), and GeneLab. From 2014, GeneLab has hosted omics data generated in investigations on the International Space Station, other spaceflight platforms, and in space-relevant ground studies (GeneLab Strategic Plan 2014, Ray et al. 2019, Berrios et al. 2021).

The establishment of the repositories and the archiving, and curation of data for public accessibility alone would have complied with the Federal mandate for open science (Holdren 2013, Nelson 2022). Principal Investigators funded by NASA to conduct biological experiments would have adhered to the obligation to deposit their data, and the story could have ended there. But four years after its creation, in 2018, GeneLab went further and implemented the Analysis Working Groups (AWGs). According to their Charter, revised in 2025, the groups “consist of members who voluntarily collaborate and engage in two main activities: One, members provide feedback on scientific standards for reuse (subject and assay metadata; processing pipelines; dataset formats and uniformed structures for machine-readability) (...) Two, AWG members collaborate to mine-reuse OSDR data to conduct scientific investigative analyses, which sometimes leads to peer-reviewed publications” (NASA OSDR, Analysis Working Group Charter 2025). Initially, each GeneLab AWG represented a model organism in the repository: plants, multi-omics, microbes, and animals (mammals and non-mammals). Later, the ALSDA and the Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning AWG were implemented with a focus on non-omics data and methods for machine readiness of data, respectively. By 2025, there are three new AWGs devoted to human data, female health, and radiation data, as well as several subgroups working on various projects.

The AWGs have brought together a broad network of approximately 600 scientists from academia, government, and industry to engage with the 995 datasets currently integrated into OSDR. In the program's words, “scientists with diverse backgrounds representing various areas of expertise form the Analysis Working Groups. Together, they process data that enables new discoveries” (GeneLab on Twitter, 2022). From the start, with the AWGs, this program made it explicit in its mode of operation that the FAIR pillars of open science, that is data findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability are a fundamentally collective endeavor. The evidential value of OSDR's data – particularly complex data given the restricted nature of the experiments that produced them – depends on the combined work and expertise of the cu-

ration teams and the AWGs. This convergence of expertise in each group has enabled new collaborations, questions, methodologies, re-examinations of existing data, insights for future experimental designs, white papers with recommendations for the future of the field, and two major publication campaigns (Cell 2020, Nature Portfolio 2024).

Alongside the significant steps taken by NASA's Science Mission Directorate to govern their data's "continued accessibility and usability for multiple decades" (NASA Science Mission Directorate 2022), the NASA's Transform to Open Science (TOPS) initiative from 2022 to 2025 centered its efforts on community building around open science practices. As stated by the TOPS program scientist, open science is not only about tools, but it is "driven by a global community with diverse perspectives" (Gentemann 2023). The TOPS initiative met scientific communities at different moments of maturity in their institutionalization and familiarity with open science practices in their domains. In the case of space biology, GeneLab had a developed experience building open science communities with the AWGs since their creation (Sanders 2024, Costes et al. 2024).

From the perspective of the PHIL_OS project, asking about the conditions under which open science can promote good research practice requires engaging in systematic examination of specific research settings. The project is an invitation to change our understanding of openness: not only – and not mainly - in terms of "availability of stuff" (data, methods, outputs), but in terms of what Sabina Leonelli, the principal investigator of the project, has defined as judicious connections. That is, the very process of building long-term connections between people making sure that sharing data entails meaningful human interactions and trust (Leonelli 2023). From this premise, OSDR and the work of the AWGs represent a unique and significant experience not only for space biology, but also for international studies on open science. For all these reasons, the workings of the groups and the expertise and experience of their members deserve careful examination.

This report builds on two resources from the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (NASEM) which depict key aspects of the space biology scientific community, and the broader Biological and Physical Sciences (BPS) Division at NASA: *Thriving in Space: Ensuring the Future of Biological and Physical Sciences Research: A Decadal Survey for 2023-2032* published in 2023, and *Foundations of a Healthy and Vital Research Community for NASA Science* published in 2022.

Both reports outlined the particular features of this research community along with its challenges. The space biology community in the United States is made up of complex interactions between institutions and individuals at the intersections of BPS, governmental agencies like the National Science Foundation and the National Institutes of Health, academic institutions, for-profit commercial entities, and international partners involved with human spaceflight (NASEM 2023, 197). Regarding individuals, the community is made up of interconnections between scientists and science managers internal and external to NASA: the agency's civil service and contractor workforce and scientists not affiliated with NASA, who, in some instances, receive funding from the agency. The various overlaps between these institutions and individuals makes tracing all the moving pieces that make up the community challenging, even when staying solely with NASA-funded investigators. In consequence, one key premise proposed by this

report to understand the results of the survey presented here is that the scientific community is not a bounded group or object. It is more fruitful to think of a community as a node for interactions and intersections of expertise and experiences (Castaño 2023), particularly when looking at a program like OSDR that continuously invites as many new participants as possible into the field.

The 2023 *Decadal* highlighted the challenges rebuilding, resourcing, and coordinating the BPS research community over the last decade after major funding cuts in the 2000s led to the departure of many researchers from the field. The report stresses that “much work remains to establish a healthy and sustainable BPS community with resources commensurate with its long-term scientific and technological mission” (NASEM 2023, 196). With these challenges in mind, the *Decadal* outlined the guide for the next decade of research providing consensus recommendations of key scientific questions, and funding increases to “build a science community in size, diversity of technical expertise and lived experience, and capability” (ibid, 216). The report recognized the slow progress in attracting and retaining historically underrepresented groups in BPS research and leadership, and stressed the need to document progress in diversity, equity, inclusion, and accessibility¹ with respect to visible and less visible characteristics of individuals.

The *Decadal* also called for the continuation of the open science infrastructure provided by GeneLab, and an expansion of “investment in open and shared computational infrastructure (CI) to support storage, analysis, and dissemination of its biological and physical data, while ensuring linkage to the original and archived samples” (ibid, 211). According to the report, these data repositories “need to be maintained by and for the broader research community” (ibid).

The *Foundations* report resulted from a request made in 2020 by the NASA Associate Administrator for SMD to the NASEM Space Studies Board to “examine the foundation or base for healthy and vital research communities” (NASEM 2022, 1). While, at the time, BPS had only been at SMD for a very short time, the findings in this report provided important guidelines for the division that converged with the *Decadal*. This report identified six attributes of community health and vitality: clear scientific questions guiding research and funding; diversity, inclusion, equity and competence across a broad range of characteristics; ongoing outreach to the larger community at all stages and the acceptance and development of its members; long cycle funding efforts to maintain and grow research communities; adaptability to changes in the human, technological, and political environment; and reinforcing recognized standards of conduct and equity in processes (ibid, 68). One key insight from the report is that tracking research communities along these lines requires more than the collection of data in which elements are treated separately. The task is to link the data to shed light on processes and trends, and to do so in a manner attentive to the particularities of the context (ibid, 2).

¹ According to NASA’s definitions that were in place from 2022 to 2025, diversity is “the entire universe of differences and similarities”; equity is “the consistent and systematic fair, just, and impartial treatment of all individuals, including individuals who belong to underserved communities”; inclusion is “the full participation, belonging, and contribution of organizations and individuals”; and accessibility involves “providing accommodations and modifications to ensure equal access to employment and participation in activities, eliminating and reducing physical barriers to promote equitable opportunities, and ensuring that every outward-facing and internal activity or electronic space can be accessed by every person independently” (NASA 2022, NASA 2024). On January 21, 2025, the agency removed the websites and reports that featured these definitions.

The results of the survey presented in the next sections substantiate the deep relationship identified by the *Decadal* and *Foundations* between the goals of addressing key scientific questions in space biology, maintaining and expanding the open science infrastructures, and building a science community in size, diversity of technical expertise and lived experience. These documents represent consensus perspectives that came into existence to inform the agency's activities. From January 21, 2025 following an Executive Order from the White House, NASA was mandated to close all its Diversity, Equity, Inclusion and Accessibility activities including websites, offices and contracts related to these issues in the agency (NASA 2025, Foust 2025). As a consequence, NASA is now mandated to not follow recommendations in the *Decadal* and *Foundations* regarding these matters.

Amidst these changes, and entering their eighth year of operations, the AWGs remain a crucial intersection of the goals of expanding the open science infrastructures and the scientific community, hence the need to characterize them as thoroughly as possible. As the results of the survey will show, data collection about these key aspects also ought to include those who participate in the AWGs who are not necessarily part of NASA-sponsored research teams since, thanks to OSDR, they are now part of the space biology community.

The results presented in this report are derived from a survey conducted between 2023 and 2024 that aimed to characterize the AWG members, their expertise, and experience participating in the groups. The survey included 30 questions and 70 respondents completed it. Out of these 70, 61 respondents were not affiliated with NASA at the time of the survey, and the remaining 9 were part of the agency working either as civil servants or contractors.

The following are the two key findings from the survey:

1. The AWGs are expanding the space biology community in four ways. First, they are bringing researchers into the field who were not previously involved with spaceflight research. Second, they are expanding the realms of expertise, skills, and scientific questions that are relevant for space biology. Third, they are including a more diverse range of individuals in terms of their demographic characteristics and career stages. And fourth, they are engaging researchers who already have experience with open science practices outside of space biology.
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Methods

The survey was conducted on Qualtrics, an online survey tool. It consisted of 30 questions (See Appendix) in five formats: multiple choice, rating, ranking, close-ended, and open-ended questions. It was available for participation from October 16, 2023 to April 12, 2024. Participation was encouraged via emails sent to the AWG mailing list in October 2023, November 2023, and April 2024, during virtual AWG meetings (Plants, ALSDA, AI/ML, Animal, and Multi-omics), and as at the in-person AWG Workshop at ASGSR in November 2023. 108 people started the survey and 70 completed it. Out of these 70, 61 are not affiliated with NASA and the remaining 9 work for the agency either as civil servants or contractors

For the purposes of this survey, the population size are all members of the AWGs, that is, approximately 600 individuals according to the latest figures from OSDR. A sample that is roughly 10% of the population size can be considered indicative and allows for making some tentative inferences about the population.

Before proceeding to the questionnaire, participants were required to complete an informed consent section. That section presented the aims and background of the survey in the PHIL_OS project, emphasizing the independent nature of the study and its funding. The section also mentioned that both the PHIL_OS project and the survey had been reviewed and approved by the Faculty of Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences Research Ethics Committee at the University of Exeter – equivalent to the Institutional Review Board (IRB) in the United States – and provided contact information if respondents had any questions.

The informed consent also specified that respondents were invited to participate because, at the time of the survey, they were over 18 years of age and were currently participating or had participated in NASA's OSDR AWGs. The section stated that participation in the survey was entirely voluntary, that participants were not going to receive payment for taking part, and that they were free to discontinue their participation at any point. The section outlined that questions would be about the expertise and experience of the respondents with the OSDR AWGs, that no information such as name or email address would be collected, and all information would be received, used, and reported in an anonymous form with the aim to make direct identification of respondents impossible. Finally, it mentioned that the results of this survey would be available in academic publications and reports and stated the commitment to share the results with the OSDR community in workshops and meetings. Preliminary results of the report were presented during the 2024 AWG Symposium on May 2nd, 2024, and during an internal meeting with OSDR and BPS staff on November 25th, 2024.

The informed consent section had two questions. First, it asked respondents to confirm that they had read and understood the above information. For those who responded “I am not sure”, the response included a note giving them the opportunity to resolve any queries with the author of this report providing contact information, or with someone else at the University of Exeter, and provided once more the contact information from the Faculty of Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences Research Ethics Committee.

The estimated time of completion of the survey was between 5 and 10 minutes. All questions gave respondents the option to answer “I prefer not to say”, and in all open required questions, the introductory section of the survey stated that respondents were free to write “I prefer not to say” if that was their preferred response.

Quantitative analysis of multiple choice, ranking, rating and close-ended questions was conducted using Qualtrics, which rounds up decimal points in reporting percentages. All open-ended questions were manually coded by the author for qualitative analysis. In the social sciences, coding refers to the categorization and labelling of qualitative data to identify patterns. Coding for those questions combined inductive and deductive approaches. Inductively, by tracking and grouping emerging themes, and deductively using the eleven Key Scientific Questions identified in the 2023 NASEM Decadal Survey for Biological and Physical Sciences in Space (NASEM 2023) as the scaffold to group responses about the topics in fundamental biology and space biology that interest respondents. For presentation purposes in open-ended questions, I included minor bracketed edits to facilitate readability.

The analysis presented here is descriptive and features all data collected for each question. There is no aim to establish causal relationships between the variables. All visualizations were produced by graphic designer Andrés Barriga.

Finally, in order to further protect the anonymity of respondents in the dataset that accompanies this report, questions that involve their assessments, evaluations, and/or feedback are presented separately and in a different order from those that characterize them. This prevents the potential identifiability of individual respondents in association with their views.

The survey results presented here are complementary to ethnographic research about the AWGs conducted by Paola Castaño which began in March 2022 and that is set to conclude in June 2025. This research has involved participant observation in 71 AWG meetings (45 of them with the Plants AWG), and 52 events hosted by OSDR, NASA TOPS, NASA Biological and Physical Sciences Division, and the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. I have also conducted interviews with 20 members of the AWGs. The thread that brings the various methods for the study together is the aim to understand the specificities of the AWGs as a mode of bringing scientists together and, from there, to trace the impact of their work for space biology. For other publications related to the OSDR case study, please visit: <https://opensciencestudies.eu/subprojects/>.

Key Findings

Finding 1: Broadening the Space Biology Community

Considering that the AWGs include scientists employed by NASA, at the start of the survey it was important to distinguish between respondents affiliated with the agency and those with no such affiliation. According to the Analysis Working Group Charter, participants cannot use their AWGs membership to claim any affiliation with NASA (NASA OSDR, Analysis Working Group Charter 2025). Out of the 70 respondents who completed the survey, 61 are not affiliated with NASA and the remaining 9 work for the agency either as civil servants or contractors

This section focuses on the 61 respondents who are not NASA or OSDR civil service and contractor workforce, and presents the four dimensions along which the OSDR AWGs are expanding the space biology community: first, by bringing in new researchers to the field of spaceflight research; second, by expanding the realm of expertise, skills, and scientific questions relevant for space biology; third, by including a more diverse range of individuals in terms of their demographic characteristics and career stages; and fourth by engaging researchers who already have experience in open science practices outside of space biology.

1.1. Beyond the Investigators Funded by NASA to Conduct Spaceflight Experiments

Who is part of the space biology community? Not too long ago, that question had a straightforward answer: those who have been involved in experiments sent to space or in ground studies relevant to spaceflight. That is, those who were directly funded to generate such data: NASA-employed scientists, principal investigators who are faculty or part of research institutions, and their teams including postdoctoral re-

searchers, students, and research staff. OSDR and the AWGs have significantly changed that picture by bringing scientists to the field who have not been previously involved with spaceflight experiments.

The two questions in the survey that provided insights into the composition of the AWGs in this regard were the following:

Are you or have you been part of a team that has designed and flown (or is already approved to fly) a spaceflight experiment?

Figure 1. Number and percentage of respondents who have been part of a team that has designed and flown (or is already approved to fly) a spaceflight experiment. 61 respondents.

Amongst the 61 respondents not affiliated with NASA, 38 of them (62%) reported that they had not been part of a team that has designed and flown – or is already approved to fly – a spaceflight experiment. As illustrated by responses to other questions in the survey, they have joined the AWGs with a diverse set of experiences and expertise to meet spaceflight data and to reanalyze them.

A concurrent although not perfectly overlapping finding regarding the expansion of the community is that most of the AWG members who responded the survey are not the ones who have deposited the data in OSDR:

Figure 2. Number and percentage of respondents who have deposited their data into NASA's OSDR. 61 respondents.

1.2. Breadth of Expertise, Skills, and Relevant Scientific Questions for Space Biology

The majority of respondents work in academia with some representation of professionals who work in industry, non-profit organizations, and government.

In which sector do you work?

Figure 4. Number and percentage of respondents in academia according to their career status. 44 respondents

For those respondents who work in academia², the survey asked about their career status with the following findings:

If you work in academia, which of the following categories best describes your career status?

Figure 4. Number and percentage of respondents in academia according to their career status. 44 respondents

VZZVVZZ Even though 44 respondents stated earlier in the survey that they worked in Academia, there were 59 responses in this question, so results were filtered for this figure.

From the standpoint of academic career status, the survey results point to a relatively young community of researchers. The combination of expertise between experienced NASA funded PIs (represented in the professor category) or members of teams that have conducted spaceflight experiments, and those joining the groups with a broader interest in bioinformatics is a key feature of the AWGs.

Two of the open-ended questions in the survey asked about the academic disciplines in which respondents conduct most of their work, and their skills. The rationale behind asking respondents to answer these two questions in their own terms is that self-definitions – as general or precise as they can be – are important when people consider what they can bring into collaborative scientific work.

The answers covered very different levels of generality in the respondents' understanding of these categories, and there was no word limit set for responses. The goal with this question was to capture one key dimension of the breadth of expertise amongst AWG members. The 61 respondents listed a total of 72 academic disciplines and fields as relevant to their work. I categorized each discipline and field in broad groups and, as expected, there are significant overlaps in key fields, so the figures include the times each subfield was mentioned.

What are the academic disciplines or fields in which you conduct most of your work?

Figure 5. Academic disciplines or fields in which respondents conduct most of their work. General Overview. The number next to each discipline or field represents the number of subcategories mentioned in each.

Figure 6. Academic disciplines or fields in which respondents conduct most of their work in Computational and data sciences. 12 subcategories. The number next to each discipline or field represents the times each subcategory was mentioned.

Figure 7. Academic disciplines or fields in which respondents conduct most of their work in Biological Sciences. 13 subcategories. The number next to each discipline or field represents the times each subcategory was mentioned.

Figure 8. Academic disciplines or fields in which respondents conduct most of their work in Biomedical Sciences, Healthcare and Specialties. 26 subcategories. The number next to each discipline or field represents the times each subcategory was mentioned.

2. Life and Physical Sciences

Figure 9. Academic disciplines or fields in which respondents conduct most of their work in Space Life Sciences. 5 subcategories. The number next to each discipline or field represents the times each subcategory was mentioned.

Figure 10. Academic disciplines or fields in which respondents conduct most of their work in Biophysics, Physics and Engineering. 7 subcategories. The number next to each discipline or field represents the times each subcategory was mentioned.

Figure 11. Academic disciplines or fields in which respondents conduct most of their work in Chemical Sciences. 4 subcategories. The number next to each discipline or field represents the times each subcategory was mentioned.

Figure 12. Academic disciplines or fields in which respondents conduct most of their work in Other Fields. 5 subcategories. The number next to each discipline or field represents the times each subcategory was mentioned.

Another open-ended question asked respondents to identify up to three of their technical skills. Just like in the previous question, all 61 respondents provided answers with different levels of understanding and generality about their skills. After grouping the 178 responses provided, there were 106 skills mentioned.

Figure 13. Technical skills reported by respondents. 61 respondents. 106 skills mentioned.

In the lists below, which specify all the skills mentioned, the number next to each skill represents the times it was mentioned by respondents:

1. Analysis Techniques/ Wet Lab Skills

14

1. RNAseq analysis (14)
2. Proteomics (5)
3. Genomics and proteomics (WB, PCR, transcriptomics) (1)
4. Gene editing (1)
5. RT-PCR [Reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction] (1)
6. Metagenomic analysis (1)
7. Human Exome Analysis (1)
8. Single cell multiomics (1)
9. Plant physiology (1)
10. Mitochondrial function measurement (1)
11. Nanopore sequencing (1)
12. Ocular Genomics (1)
13. Tear Proteomics (1)
14. Assessment of microbial communities via culturing and sequencing (1)

2. Analysis Techniques

31

1. Programming (R, python and Javascript) (14)
2. Statistical analysis (12)
3. Data analysis [general] (6)
4. Machine Learning [general] (6)
5. Bioinformatics (5)
6. Genome assembly (2)
7. Modelling (mathematical, pathways) (2)
8. Omics data analysis (1)
9. Computational data analysis (1)
10. Genomic Seq [general] (1)
11. Gene expression analysis (1)
12. Electrophoresis (1)
13. Spatial transcriptomics (1)

14. DNA analysis (1)
15. Amplicon sequencing (1)
16. Structural equation modelling and other multivariate statistics (1)
17. Graph analysis (1)
18. Data visualization (1)
19. Omics analysis (1)
20. Omics data analysis (1)
21. Methylation analysis (1)
22. Network analysis (1)
23. Metabolomic analysis (1)
24. Lipidomic analysis (1)
25. Data consolidation (1)
26. Computer vision (1)
27. Neural networks (1)
28. Computational biophysics (1)
29. Gene and gene family nomenclature and functional annotation (1)
30. Genomic Variant Analysis (1)
31. JMARS [Geographic information system] (1)

3. Wet Lab Skills

▼ 32

1. Cell culture (6)
2. Confocal microscopy (4)
3. Wet Lab Skills [general] (4)
4. PCR [Polymerase Chain Reaction] (4)
5. Immunohistochemistry (2)
6. NGS [Next Generation Sequencing] wet lab skills (1)
7. Molecular biology wet lab skills (1)
8. Wet lab experiments (e.g. western blot, PCR, gene modification-transfection-, advanced imaging, flow cytometry, etc) (1)
9. Plant stress biology experiments (1)
10. Rodent brain surgeries (1)
11. Biological-mass spectrometry (1)
12. Embryo manipulation (1)
13. Gas chromatography (1)
14. Cell viability assays (1)
15. Chromatin analysis (1)
16. Cellular toxicology (1)
17. Electrochemistry (1)
18. Plant genome and transcriptome sequencing and analysis (1)

19. Flow cytometry (1)
20. XRD [X-ray diffraction] (1)
21. Laboratory automation (1)
22. Hyperspectral imaging (1)
23. Biochemistry analysis (1)
24. Ocular Investigations (Anterior Segment-OCT, Pentacam, Confocal Microscopy) (1)
25. Histology (IF microscopy, IF confocal) (1)
26. Genomics sample processing (1)
27. ELISA [Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay] (1)
28. Southern blot (1)
29. Single cell analysis (1)
30. Cell biology (1)
31. Cloning (1)
32. Molecular cloning (1)

4. Study Design and Management Skills

5

1. Study design including statistical plan (1)
2. Statistical plan (1)
3. IRB protocol writing, consent (1)
4. Clinical trial coordination (multi-site studies too) (1)
5. Project management (1)

5. Making and Designing Skills

7

1. Design [general] (2)
2. 3D bioprinting (2)
3. Hardware design (2)
4. Biosensors (2)
5. 3D printing (1)
6. Medical device development (design) (1)
7. Designing and making regolith simulants (1)

6. Medical Skills

1. Drug development (1)
2. Dental anamnesis and diagnostics (1)
3. Clinical reasoning (1)
4. ART [Assisted reproductive technologies] (1)
5. Memory assessments in human and animals (1)
6. Brain imaging methods, MRI and PET (1)
7. Behavior (1)
8. Epidemiology (1)

7. Other Skills

1. Biophysics (2)
2. Engineering (2)
3. Evidence synthesis (1)
4. Systematic review (1)
5. Knowledge synthesis (1)
6. Scientific Communication (1)
7. Security traffic management (1)
8. Natural systems including natural history (1)
9. Cloud computing (1)

The breadth of disciplines, fields and skills in this group of responses paints a very rich landscape of expertise and conveys that there is not a 'right' kind of scientific background to participate in these groups, but that breadth of perspectives and potential complementarity in interactions are the key.

The survey also included open-ended questions about the space biology and fundamental scientific questions that interest respondents most. I categorized all responses using the themes and key questions defined by *Thriving in Space: Ensuring the Future of Biological and Physical Sciences Research: A Decadal Survey for 2023-2032* as a scaffold. While the *Decadal's* questions encompass both the biological and physical sciences, and not all were used for the categorization of responses, they provide a framework for the grouping of the scientific interests represented by AWG members and their direct relevance for space biology.

Key Scientific Questions in Biological and Physical Sciences Space Research Over the Decade 2023-2032

Themes	Key Scientific Questions
Theme 1 Adapting to space	1.1 How does the space environment influence biological mechanisms required for organisms to survive the transitions to and from space, and thrive while off Earth? 1.2 How do genetic diversity and life history influence physiological adaptation to the space environment? 1.3 How does the space environment alter interactions between organisms?
Theme 2 Living and traveling in space	2.1 What are the important multi-generational effects of the space environment on growth, development, and reproduction? 2.2 What principles guide the integration of biological and abiotic systems to create sustainable and functional extraterrestrial habitats? 2.3 What principles enable identification, extraction, processing, and use of materials found in extraterrestrial environments to enable long-term, sustained human and robotic space exploration? 2.4 What are the relevant chemical and physical properties and phenomena that govern the behavior of fluids in space environments?
Theme 3 Probing phenomena hidden by gravity or terrestrial limitations	3.1 What are the mechanisms by which organisms sense and respond to physical properties of surroundings and to applied mechanical forces, including gravitational force? 3.2 What are the fundamental principles that organize the structure and functionality of materials, including but not limited to soft and active matter? 3.3 What are the fundamental laws that govern the behavior of systems that are far from equilibrium? 3.4 What new physics, including particle physics, general relativity, and quantum mechanics, can be discovered with experiments that can only be carried out in space?

Figure 14. Adapted from Key Scientific Questions in Biological and Physical Sciences Research. *Thriving in Space: Ensuring the Future of Biological and Physical Sciences Research: A Decadal Survey for 2023-2032* (NASSEM 2023)

The overarching goal of space biology is to understand how life responds to the spaceflight environment, and how it re-adapts to Earth. In this regard, all questions can be characterized as part of the realm of studies of biological stress which examine responses and adaptations of organisms to unusual environmental conditions. Looking at the questions in more detail, most of them speak directly to the three themes outlined by the *Decadal* and the key scientific questions for this research community.

Figure 15. Space Biology Questions that interest respondents. General Overview. 61 respondents. 72 questions mentioned.

Figure 16. Space Biology Questions that interest respondents grouped in Theme 1 of the *Decadal Survey* Key Scientific questions.

Below are all the questions listed by respondents in the survey that are pertinent to Theme 1 categorized by question and, in the relevant instances, subcategorized in terms of the species they tackle:

1.1 How does the space environment influence biological mechanisms required for organisms to survive the transitions to and from space, and thrive while off Earth?
38

20 Human/
 Animals

1. How does long-term exposure to microgravity in space affect the composition and function of the human microbiome?
2. Effects of spaceflight on the skin.
3. Health preservation of astronaut crew members.
4. Alterations in human skin in space.
5. How traveling for a long time in space might affect our bodies at cellular levels. This includes thinking about how things like floating in space, being exposed to space radiation, and other

space-related challenges might change how our bodies work. Understanding these changes is important for planning long trips to places like Mars and for figuring out how to keep astronauts healthy during those trips

6. Space Health & Medicine.
7. Space Health & Wellness.
8. Spaceflight Associated Neuro-Ocular Syndrome, Impact of Microgravity on Eye & Vision, Effect of Deep Exploration on the Eye.
9. Human genes and how human health and mind change in space.
10. Space medicine for space stressors related to astronaut health
11. How does spaceflight affect astronaut health?
12. How presence/lack of magnetic fields can affect the organism.
13. What are the effects of spaceflight on the brain and behavior?
14. Long-term missions to Moon and Mars.
15. Impact of spaceflight on the brain.
16. How to stay healthy in space.
17. How space affects the organism.
18. How microgravity can affect human health.
19. Biomarkers.
20. Biomedical advancement.

7 Plants

1. How can we learn from nature to help plants deal with the stress and adapting to microgravity or the challenges associated with space travel?
2. How can plants thrive in space and earth environment[s] to support sustainable food requirements?
3. How do the compounding stresses of space affect plants?
4. How do we reliably grow plants or algae in space?
5. How can plants best adapt to the spaceflight environment for crop production?
6. Molecular mechanisms plants require to adapt [to the] space environment.
7. How do plants adapt to microgravity environments?

11 General

1. Adaptations to space
2. Effects of radiation and microgravity on biology.
3. Physiological alterations induced by spaceflight.
4. Mutation.
5. Diseases.
6. Infections.
7. Impact of microgravity.
8. Responses of Earth life in extraterrestrial environment.

9. Combined effects
10. How [microgravity] can affect life in general.
11. How cells respond and adapt to space.

1.2 **How do genetic diversity and life history influence physiological adaptation to the space environment?**

1

1. What are the psychophysiological effects of living in space long term, and how are they affected when provided biophilic links to Earth?

1.3 **How does the space environment alter interactions between organisms?**

3

3 **Microbes**

1. How will microbial ecology impact our life support goals for space missions and how can they be optimized to benefit them?
2. Microbes and humans.
3. How do different physiological systems interact and influence each other in microgravity?

Figure 17. Space Biology Questions that interest respondents grouped in Theme 2 of the *Decadal Survey* Key Scientific questions.

2.1 What are the important multi-generational effects of the space environment on growth, development, and reproduction?
8

Below are all the questions listed by respondents in the survey that are pertinent to Theme 2 categorized by question and, in the relevant instances, subcategorized in terms of the species they tackle:

6 Human/Animals

1. Reproduction in space.
2. Will reproduction be possible in space?
3. How will life evolve on other planetary bodies.
4. Pregnancy in space.
5. How can we ensure that all humans stay healthy throughout the missions required to establish humanity as a multi-planet species?
6. Multiple stressor effects on the health outcomes as it relates to standard development.

2 Plants

1. Plant longevity in space settlement.
2. Reliable and scalable crop production, in-situ resource utilization.

2.2 What principles guide the integration of biological and abiotic systems to create sustainable and functional extraterrestrial habitats?

2

1. The role of plants like legumes in the nitrogen cycling in closed space ecosystems (ISS, Moon, Mars)
2. Advancing human exploration with bioregenerative approaches and bioastronautics

* Applications and countermeasures

5

1. How do we feed people in space?
2. [Can] the DNA damage response in an astronaut be tackled using FDA approved specific small molecule inhibitors?
3. How can we translate space biology findings to building production systems?
4. What's the translation aspect to terrestrial care.
5. Radiation protection.

Figure 18. Space Biology Questions that interest respondents grouped in Theme 3 of the *Decadal Survey* Key Scientific questions.

Below are all the questions listed by respondents in the survey that are pertinent to Theme 3 categorized by question:

3.1 What are the mechanisms by which organisms sense and respond to physical properties of surroundings and to applied mechanical forces, including gravitational force?
6

1. The influence of extended periods of exposure to radiation in a microgravity environment on physiological functions and the molecular pathways potentially responsible for their alterations.
2. How and why biology is affected in low orbit and in deep space.
3. How spaceflight affects mitochondria pathways analogous to neurodegeneration?
4. What are the predominant multiomic alterations within a cancer cell flown to space.
5. What are the epigenetic changes triggered by the space conditions?
6. Aspects molecular [Molecular aspects] of the species evolution and reverse ecology.

* Applications and countermeasures

5

1. Microgravity biophysics.
2. Radiation.
3. Microgravity.
4. Extreme environments.
5. Quantum behavior in the brain.

Finally, there were a few responses that pointed to areas different from those outlined by the Decadal survey:

Others

4 Questions

1.
Astrobiology
3 Questions

1. Life [on] other planets.
2. The possibilities of the existence of life beyond earth.
3. Exobiology.

2.
Literature
1 Questions

1. Human space exploration literature.

Another question aligned with the former asked respondents about the fundamental biology question that most interests them. This question received 57 responses which I also categorized using the *Decadal Survey* themes and scientific questions to highlight their direct relevance for space biology.

Figure 19. Fundamental Biology Questions that interest respondents. General Overview. 57 questions.

Figure 20. Fundamental Biology Questions that interest respondents grouped in Theme 1 of the *Decadal Survey* Key Scientific questions.

Below are all the questions listed by respondents in the survey that are pertinent to Theme 1 categorized by question:

1.1 **How does the space environment influence biological mechanisms required for organisms to survive the transitions to and from space, and thrive while off Earth?**

11

1. Radiation effects on metabolism.
2. What are the epigenetic changes triggered by the space conditions.
3. How does our physiology change in microgravity.
4. Effects of space travel on the body.
5. Human body plasticity.
6. Muscle health, metabolism.
7. Formation of memory.
8. How do the cardiovascular and skeletal systems depend on each other and how can these processes be modelled to predict disease?
9. How does the lung architecture or phenome vary in astronauts.
10. How does microgravity affect vertebrates.
11. Effect of Microgravity Eye, SANS, Ocular Genomics & Proteomics, Ocular Microbiomes, Tear Biomarkers.

1.2 **How do genetic diversity and life history influence physiological adaptation to the space environment?**

3

1. The fundamental initiating event of a mutation.
2. Understanding the genetic regulatory regions that make organisms distinct.
3. Regulation and evolution of genome, epigenome.

Figure 21. Fundamental Biology Questions that interest respondents grouped in Theme 2 of the *Decadal Survey* Key Scientific questions.

Below are all the questions listed by respondents in the survey that are pertinent to Theme 2 categorized by question:

2.1 What are the important multi-generational effects of the space environment on growth, development, and reproduction? 4

1. What mechanisms underlie the evolutionary adaptation and diversification of fundamental life processes in response to dynamic environmental pressures?
2. How do microbial trait adaptations to stresses allow them to dominate communities and dictate functions.
3. Migration of life in space.
4. How do we make plants and algae more efficient at what they do?

2.2 **What principles guide the integration of biological and abiotic systems to create sustainable and functional extraterrestrial habitats?**
 4

1. How to use agriculture when colonizing planets to meet the nutritional, medicinal, and psychological needs of crew.
2. Multispecies ecological dynamics in bioregenerative life support systems.
3. Driving mechanisms of soil microbiomes in soil development/chemistry/nutrient availability and up-take.
4. Which are the fundamental components for life on other planets?

Theme 3

Probing phenomena hidden by gravity or terrestrial limitations

17 Questions

3.1 **What are the mechanisms by which organisms sense and respond to physical properties of surroundings and to applied mechanical forces, including gravitational force?**
 17

Figure 22. Fundamental Biology Questions that interest respondents grouped in Theme 3 of the *Decadal Survey* Key Scientific questions.

Below are all the questions listed by respondents in the survey that are pertinent to Theme 3 categorized by question:

3.1 **What are the mechanisms by which organisms sense and respond to physical properties of surroundings and to applied mechanical forces, including gravitational force?**
 4

1. What is the mechanism and origin of gravity sensing?
2. Mechanisms behind plant adaptation to environmental stimulus.
3. Molecular mechanism of the species adaptation.

4. How do organisms adapt to stress environments that they have never encountered before?
5. How plants respond to their environment and adapt.
6. Telomere changes under stress.
7. Effect of non-coding RNAs in organism adaptations.
8. Redox regulation leading to damage under space conditions.
9. How do plants communicate and how important is this social network for them?
10. How does gene expression regulate cell function.
11. Mitochondrial and biophysics.
12. Mitochondrial dynamics.
13. How plants coordinate the different regulatory mechanisms under stress condition.
14. Quantum behavior in the brain.
15. Cellular and Molecular Biology.
16. Protein changes due to space travel and mutation rates.
17. Indirect biophysical diffusion stress and space radiation.

Finally, there were a few responses that pointed to areas different from those outlined by the Decadal survey:

☰ Others

18 Questions

I. Origins of life

6 Questions

1. How life possibly began
2. The origin of life
3. Evolution and the origin of life
4. What is the true origin of life in the solar system?
5. Origin of life on Earth
6. How is Life possible on other planets? In which form?

2.

Disease**4** Questions

1. How can we diagnose tumors early and get better treatments?
2. What are the biological individual differences that predispose humans to diseases like cancers, and detrimental physiological changes during spaceflight? Bonus, what can we do about these (personalised medicine)?
3. How space travel affects the ageing process and overall health span of astronauts. Specifically, I want to understand how factors like microgravity and cosmic radiation influence ageing and senescence in space, and how these changes impact astronauts' health during long missions. This research not only helps us keep astronauts healthy in space but also provides insights into ageing-related health issues on Earth.
4. Find answers to conditions and diseases in multiomic information.

3.

Biology and epistemology**5** Questions

1. How can we understand biology as a quantitative collection of molecules.
2. How to turn biology into an engineering discipline.
3. How do we have networks in every systems we can think of?
4. How to get more math involved.
5. What are the critical events that can be used to inform risk model development.

4.

General**3** Questions

1. Everything
2. How human system works
3. Many, why we grow[th] what we grow[th].

Finally, regarding the scientific worlds that intersect in the AWGs, the survey asked respondents in which professional associations they are members. This was an open-ended question, thus respondents had different understandings of what constitutes a professional society. The answers are listed below and the numbers in bracket represent the times each association was mentioned:

Please indicate in which professional associations you are a member, if any

American Society of Gravitational and Space Research (ASGSR) (18)
 NASA AWG (4)
 American Society of Plant Biologists (ASPB) (9)
 Radiation Research Society (3)
 American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA) (3)
 American Association for Cancer Research (AACR) (2)
 American Physical Society (APS) (2)
 Aerospace Medical Association (ASMA) (2)
 Botanical Society of America (2)
 International Society for Gravitational Physiology (ISGP) (2)
 Cochrane (2)
 American Geophysical Union (AGU) (2)
 American College of Occupational and Environmental Medicine (ACOEM) (2)
 Australasian Proteomics Society (2)
 Student European Low Gravity Research Association (SELGRA) (2)
 International Bureau for Epilepsy (IBE) (2)
 Society for Neuroscience (2)
 University Honor Societies (2)
 Metabolomics Association of North America (MANA) (2)
 Aerospace Medicine Student & Resident Organization (AMSRO)
 AgBioData Consortium
 AllMS Scientist Association (ASA), India
 All India Society of Cell Biology
 American Academy of Forensic Sciences
 American Academy of Sleep Medicine (AASM)
 American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS)
 American Association of Sleep Medicine
 American College of Sports Medicine (ASCM)
 American Heart Association (AHA)
 American Institute for Medical and Biological Engineering (AIMBE)
 American Osteopathic College of Occupational and Preventive Medicine
 American Physiological Society
 American Society for Mass Spectrometry (ASMS)
 American Society of Plant Biologists
 ANMA –Associazione Nazionale Medici d’Azienda e Competenti
 Austrian Space Forum (OeWF)
 Blue Marble Space Institute of Science
 British Interplanetary Society
 British society of immunology
 Canadian Space Health Research Network
 Clay Minerals Society (CMS)
 Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología [Mexico] (CONAHCYT)
 COVID-19 International Research Team (COVIRT)
 Development Committee, World Council of Optometry (WCO)
 Ecological Society of America,
 European Society of Human Reproduction and Embryology (ESHRE)
 Florida Native Plant Society
 General medical Council, UK Space Labs,

Geological Society of America (GSA)
Human Proteome Organization (HUPO)
Indian Optometry Association (IOA), India
Indian Society of Cornea & Intensive care society
International Brain Research Organization (IBRO)
International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES)
International Society for Biocuration (ISB)
International Society for Extracellular Vesicles (ISEV)
International society for gravitational physiology
International Society for Neurochemistry
International Society of Nephrology (ISN)
International Society to Advance Alzheimer's Research and Treatment (ISTAART)
IUCN Commission member United Nation Environment Programme member of youth constituency
Keratorefractive Surgeons (ISCKRS), India
Mars on Earth Project (MoEP)
Mycological Society of America,
National Technical Investigators' Association (NTAIA)
Physiology Society
Royal Aeronautical Society, England,
Royal College of Anesthesia
Royal College of Physicians
Scientific Society for Astrobiology (SSA)
Scleral Lens Education Society (SLS), USA
Società Italiana della Riproduzione Umana (SIRU)
Society for Neuroscience (SFN)
Society for Reproductive Investigation (SRI)
Society for Women in Engineering (SWE)
Soil Ecology Society
Soil Science Society of America (SSSA)
Space Generation Advisory Council (SGAC)
UK National Space Academy

1.3 Demographic and Career-stage Diversity

Another important dimension of the diversity in the AWGs is the demographic one. Acknowledging that lived experience is complex and multidimensional and cannot be confined to demographic indicators, this section presents some indicative data about gender, ethnicity, career state, and country of work. One limitation of this survey is that it did not ask about disability and other accessibility-related issues

Regarding gender, these were the responses:

What is your gender identity?

Figure 23. Number and percentage of respondents' gender identity. 61 respondents.

Regarding ethnicity, the survey used categories broadly based on those used in census data in the United States and United Kingdom, and asked respondents to add the ethnic category that best suited them:

What is your ethnicity?

Figure 24. Number and percentage of respondents' ethnicity. 60 respondents. Under the category "My ethnicity is best described as" the two respondents identified as Aboriginal and Kurdish.

One benchmark to assess data on gender and ethnicity is the most recent report of the STEM workforce conducted by the United States Census Bureau in 2021. This report indicates that, despite women representing 51% of the overall population in the country, they account for only 35% of the STEM workforce (NCSES 2023). Furthermore, the STEM field has historically exhibited significant disparities among various ethnic groups, with white researchers maintaining a predominant presence. It is important to note that this data primarily pertains to the United States, and a substantial portion of the respondents in the AWGs are located outside of this country (Figure 25). However, OSDR operates as a US-based institution. Considering these factors and the considerable differences in population sizes, the survey findings suggest that the AWGs have a higher representation of women (41% of respondents) and individuals from non-white ethnic backgrounds (52% of respondents) compared to other STEM organizations in the United States.

Regarding country of work, almost half of the respondents to the survey are located outside the United States, which highlights the increasingly international nature of the AWGs:

Figure 25. Respondents' country of work by numbers. 60 respondents.

Finally, regarding age and in relation to the question about career stage, responses present a picture of the AWGs as a relatively young community with a majority of early career academics amongst respondents:

What is your age group?

Figure 26. Respondents' age group by numbers. 61 respondents.

1.4 Familiarity with open science practices

The survey asked about respondents' familiarity with open science practices outside OSDR. Three questions aimed to shed light on the fact that the AWGs are engaging researchers who already have experience with open science practices outside of space biology.

Have you used open databases other than NASA's OSDR?

Figure 27. Number and percentage of respondents who have used open databases other than NASA's OSDR. 61 respondents.

Have you deposited data into an open database other than NASA's OSDR?

Figure 28. Number and percentage of respondents who have deposited data into an open database other than NASA's OSDR. 61 respondents.

Have you worked as a paid staff member or as a volunteer in an open database other than NASA's OSDR?

Figure 29. Number and percentage of respondents who have worked as a paid staff member or as a volunteer in an open database other than NASA's OSDR. 61 respondents.

In these questions most respondents reported having used open databases other than NASA's OSDR, and a few of them even had operational experience either as paid staff members or volunteers, and almost half had deposited data into one or more open databases different from OSDR. This finding is relevant for one key role of the AWGs which is to provide feedback to the repository regarding analysis pipelines, metadata standards, and other aspects of its data systems.

2. Finding 2: Diverse and Mostly Positive Experiences of Participation

2.1. Characteristics of Participation in AWGs

The survey asked respondents in which AWG or AWGs they participate, allowing for the selection of multiple applicable groups. At the time of the survey, the options listed were the only existing AWGs. Out of the 61 respondents, 38 participate in more than one AWG with Multi-omics being the one group with the largest membership. In this regard, the survey results are consistent with the general characteristics of the AWG community.

In which AWG or AWGs do you participate? (Please select all that apply)
– by responses not respondents)

Figure 30. AWG or AWGs in which respondents participate. 61 respondents, 130 responses.

Additionally, respondents were asked when they joined their main AWG and, again, consistently with data reported by the program, 2023 was the year with the most significant increase in AWG membership:

When did you first join the AWG or AWGs in which you participate?

Figure 31. Year in which respondents first joined the AWG or AWGs in which they participate. 61 respondents.

Aiming to delve a bit deeper into the degree of involvement with the groups, another question asked about the weekly hours that respondents devote to AWG-related work. Most respondents reported an average of 2-8 weekly hours:

Considering an average week in the last month (or less if you have joined more recently), how many hours per week did you spend on AWG-related work?

Figure 32. Hours per week that respondents spend on AWG-related work considering an average week in the last month (or less if they have joined the group more recently). 61 respondents.

2.2 Outcomes and Goals of Participation in the AWGs

One key question that shed light on the diverse nature of respondents' participation in the AWGs and their different outcomes addressed their involvement in publications:

wFigure 33. Number and percentage of respondents who have been co-authors in any peer-reviewed publication (accepted for publication or already published) resulting from their work in an AWG or AWGs. 61 respondents.

For those who participated in publications, less than half of the respondents, the survey asked about the nature of their participation with the following outcomes.

If your answer was “yes” in the previous question, please indicate in which role you participated (please select all that apply)

Figure 34. Roles in which AWG members participated when co-authoring a publication. 27 respondents.

The fact that more than half of the respondents had not co-authored papers resulting from their participation in the AWGs invites a consideration about how to capture the groups' work beyond this key output. The next question further specified other activities in which respondents had collaborated with their fellow AWG members.

In which of the following activities have you collaborated with members of your AWG or AWGs

Figure 35. Activities different from publications in which respondents have collaborated with members of their AWG or AWGs. 61 respondents. Those who answered 'Other' did not specify their roles.

These findings paint a rich picture of interactions and outcomes that go beyond publications. Most saliently, the fact that most respondents reported that they had provided feedback on each other's work points to the building of relationships of trust amongst AWG members.

Regarding respondents' motivations to participate in the group, the survey asked them to rank provided options by dragging them up or down to their desired positions. Aside from the fact that answering space biology questions is a top motivation for most respondents, there is not a clear pattern in the answers, which points to the fact that people join the groups with a wide range of goals in mind.

What are your top motivations to participate in the AWGs?

Figure 36. Motivations to participate in the group ranked by category, who answered 'Other' did not specify their motivation.

2.3. Members' Evaluations of Aspects of OSDR, their AWGs, and their Experiences of Participation

The survey inquired about the extent to which respondents considered that the metadata from OSDR accurately represents the experiments. 70% of the respondents stated that it does so very closely or somewhat closely. Work on metadata standards has been a key effort in the repository's work, and one domain in which various subject matter experts have provided crucial feedback to the program. Consequently, these responses reflect a favorable assessment of these efforts.

How closely would you say the metadata from OSDR characterizes the experiments?

Figure 37. Respondent's assessment of metadata in the repository. 61 respondents.

Another evaluative question in the survey asked respondents to assess the performance of the main AWG in which they participate in all the following aspects. The responses show a mostly positive evaluations in all aspects:

Considering the main AWG in which you participate, please evaluate the performance of the groups in these aspects:

Gaining new insights from existing data

Involving students

Integrating expertise from different disciplines

Keeping a core membership

Publishing papers re-analyzing OS DR data

Seeking support from OS DR with specific datasets or technical

Developing new methods

Developing new models

Designing new experiments

Writing grant proposals

Figure 38. Respondents' evaluations of the performance of their main AWG in different aspects. 61 respondents.

Finally, the survey had three open-ended questions that aimed to gain further insights into the respondents' experiences in the AWGs. For these last three questions, the full dataset with NASA-affiliated respondents is included. I eliminated the answers in which people stated, "I am not sure", "I do not know", or "N/A".

The first of these open questions asked respondents for their considerations about positive and/or negative aspects of their experience participating in the AWGs. Out of the 70 respondents in the survey, 53 took the time to answer this question. In some cases, a single response had more than one statement, thus, in total, this section covers 61 statements. They are categorized along the lines of the framing question in positive and negative aspects. Within this general categorization, there is a further distinction between statements that refer to different levels: institutional (OSDR/NASA), group (AWG), individual (researcher). There were 39 positive statements, some of which were general and did not specify any of these levels. 12 statements pointed to negative aspects in respondent's assessments of the operations of the groups along the same levels (institution, group, and individual). Finally, there were 10 statements that had a suggested course of action in which the evaluative statement was implicit.

Figure 39. Respondent's considerations about positive and/or negative aspects of their experience participating in the AWGs. 53 respondents. 61 statements.

Below are all the answers in each category and subcategory:

☰ Positive 39

1. General

6

1. Overall very positive.
2. Everything is outstanding and splendid.
3. Excellent AWG and NASA GeneLab.
4. I don't have any suggestions because I think it's been a great experience.
5. All positive.
6. It has been excellent.

2. Institution

2

1. From my point of view, NASA in most ways leads federal data archiv[ing] from public studies.
2. I believe that the work done in Genelab and similar projects is paving the way for this exploration to become a reality. It's incredible to see dedicated and committed individuals working tirelessly to make this dream come true. Through initiatives like Genelab, we can envision an exciting and promising future for space exploration, where science and technology come together to propel humanity to new horizons.

3. Groups

21

1. The AWG is a really nice community.
2. The AWG community is very open, I believe everyone feels welcome and they belong.
3. I think that the AWG is a fantastic and important collaborative workspace to showcase the space biology community. It shows that science is welcoming and open to all, to help others. achieve the combined goal to utilize the current data to help uncover new connections.
4. People and community are very friendly!
5. It is an outstanding group.
6. AWG is providing [a] platform to all space enthusiasts to come together and help in collaborations and building connections.
7. AWG I participate in is very friendly, positive and productive group.
8. I am impressed that the AWGs are inclusive and navigating new ways to work.
9. I appreciate how welcoming the groups have been.
10. Each AWG has [a] different system and all seem [to be] working well.
11. Other than the opportunity to further utilize the space flight experiments to do further research and advance knowledge the AWGs are a great way to produce science in a non-competitive environment.

12. The current emphasis on training the groups in open science is laudable.
13. Very friendly and supportive community.
14. I have only had the opportunity to attend one session so far since joining. The host was fantastic; he came prepared.
15. Great informative meetings.
16. I love the collaborative approach of the group.
17. Collegiality.
18. I like it [i]s a diverse group of people all trying to work through a common issue.
19. A great group of people open to all kinds of ideas and very knowledgeable in their field.
20. I enjoyed how open and friendly the environment is[,] especially to newcomers.
21. I have had positive experiences with the AWG groups, people are nice and want to involve students and it is exciting.

4. Individual 10

1. I enjoy all collaborations I participated in and [I am] looking forward to collaborating on new ideas and projects.
2. I don't have sufficient time to be as fully engaged with the AWGs as I would like.
3. Particularly good for early career development, such as via internship opportunities or opportunities to be involved with publications.
4. The workshop [ASGSR 2023] was great and very helpful as a new AWG member. I am still getting to know AWG and have not had the time bandwidth to participate at a significant level as of yet, but as an early career person it is a great resource that I look forward to getting more involved in as I am able.
5. I'm in a peer review process based on a manuscript developed with Open information, has been a great experience.
6. Engagement in AWGs presents substantial opportunities for professional development, interdisciplinary collaboration, and meaningful contributions to the field of space exploration.
7. I love meeting new contacts.
8. I appreciate that the organization is flexible (for example, sometimes we are personally very busy and cannot attend meetings, but it is ok).
9. My participation in Genelab has deeply inspired me to believe in the potential of human exploration in space.
10. I'm an MD/PhD and took time off to learn machine learning and also have a break. Open science initiatives like Genelab plays an invaluable role in enabling professionals like me, particularly women who may need to take breaks from their careers due to family responsibilities or other reasons, to continue contributing to their fields at their own pace and without the pressure of deadlines. It also provided me a platform to apply and practice new skills, such as machine learning, while still staying connected to my field [...] Lastly, I did work in wetlab during my PhD and post-doctoral fellowship. However, I didn't see myself running a lab which requires a lot of administrative tasks and writing grants, although I still enjoy doing research. Especially for physician scientists like me who prefer to focus on clinic but do not want to disconnect from research, AWS enables an alternative option. Since the data is already processed, without doing hands on mice experiments or immunohistochemistry, one can still analyze and interpret the data based on the knowledge and experiences s/he acquired in the wetlab. In the past years, I had never considered going to private practice as I used to think leaving academia would make me disconnect from research. These days, with open science initiatives as Genelab, I started considering it.

☰ Negative 12

1. Institution

2

1. There is almost very little and no funding available for re-use and reanalysis of the plant OSDR data.
2. Because this an evolving field, there are many growing pains. I think many of the people in the data curation team are underqualified and don't hold the expertise required to perform their work.

2. Group

7

1. It is difficult to get them to work on collaborative research papers. Generally one or 2 people seem to team up to get a group paper done. I wish I knew how to get more teams working together to submit papers on behalf of the group as a whole.
2. A bit like chasing cats to keep them going.
3. I am concerned that the AWGs do not always protect trainees from conflicts of interest and/or professional issues associated with AWG work/projects.
4. The current emphasis on training the groups in open science is laudable, but it has caused the plant group to lose focus on developing research ideas from the open access data.
5. Standard challenges in project management and delegation. Early career collaborators can be granted an inappropriate level of responsibility.
6. Some challenges with timezones, but understandable due to US focus.
7. Focus is sometimes lacking and many discussions are intimidating to students, new people, rank and file.

3. Individual

3

1. Sometimes it is challenging to be involved, but it's hard to say why. Perhaps the virtual setting, but I am also not very familiar with opportunities to collaborate.
2. I wish I had more time to devote to them, it's very much a "you get out what you put in" and unfortunately, I haven't been able to put much in.
3. Since it's a volunteer group, it's difficult to prioritize time towards it.

≡ Suggested courses of action ▼ 10

1. The ALSDA AWG spends a lot of time on standards, which I understand, but I wish there were more projects reusing data.
2. Holding a public forum to consult academics and thought leaders on this work is overwhelmingly a good idea that most importantly builds and strengthens the community, but some of the guidance requests by AWG are alarmingly basic and initiatives fall short [of] what should be expected from the world's leading space and computational biologists.
3. One obstacle I encountered was the lack of an affiliation option when submitting publications. This is indeed a challenge, as many publication submission systems may not have a "no affiliation" option in their drop-down menus. I believe we need a greater recognition in affiliation requirements in research and academic publishing to promote inclusivity. Professionals still should be able to exist without an affiliation and share their knowledge and experience.
4. Having a formal recognition/affiliation would be great.
5. It's good to signpost students to this.
6. I wish I could see all the possible projects in one place so I could read about them and decide which project to join in. Maybe because I am a new member too.
7. I think that the plant AWG has done better on generating ideas and following through when there was clear leadership. We have talked about elections multiple times when leadership was first shifting but I don't think anything came of it.
8. This involvement [with the AWGs] also introduces complex challenges that necessitate meticulous consideration and strategic management.
9. Strong personalities sometimes need to regulate time used for equity in conversations.
10. - Most important is coordination among all group members and regional timing for any activities. A dedicated team leader should be appointed to execute events properly. Also, It is necessary to appoint a regional country representative or point-of-contact person for better management as per the WHO framework.

Another open-ended question asked about suggestions for strategies to encourage broader involvement in utilization of OSDR data. This question received 49 responses which included 55 statements. Most of the statements focused on a set of institutional resources and practices that respondents suggested could be improved, and a smaller subset centered on the workings of the groups.

Figure 40. Respondents' suggested strategies to encourage broader involvement in tilization of OSDR data. 49 respondents. 56 statements.

Below are all the answers in each category and subcategory:

≡ Group ▼ 4

1. Project management 1

1. Initial planning of new projects first by (or with) senior/experienced members and then delegation of smaller parts to junior/early career members. Due to the nature of research projects can be fairly freeform, but some initial planning of scope and structure could aid project success and help to prevent projects from hanging. This could also serve as an opportunity to involve expert researchers who may not be involved in space biology, for example during the planning of a new project on retina analysis, a presentation from an expert ophthalmologist could be organised, and they could become involved in the project.

2. Focus 1

1. I value that students are able to join the AWG, but its historical purpose was not education. For example, the AI/ML AWG needs to focus on the research itself, not trying to educate people what AI/ML is.

3. General 2

1. Collaborations
2. Connecting people with similar interests.

≡ Institution ▼ 46

1. Outreach ▼ 12

1. Go to more conferences, events, seminars, and meet more researchers, invite them to join.
2. Involvement in university courses, I would love to take some datasets through a course and observe the results a cohort could perform.

3. I do not know. I often think about this. I do think it would help to have people sharing about the repository at more conferences outside of the space research community, to get people who are actively involved in Earth research to consult and lend their insights into space research.
4. Many people are intimidated by the NASA aspect of the AWGs. More should be done to encourage people of different backgrounds to join.
5. Increased student outreach.
6. Make outreach programs through universities.
7. Make it obvious how free and open source it is.
8. To include more scientists, researchers, and graduate professionals in more debate and discussion.
9. I believe most institutions especially in Europe do not know about OSDR. More awareness will lead to more involvement and better utilization of the data.
10. Get teachers involved in using it in the classroom.
11. Outreach and advertising the initiative.
12. Incentivize people to store data in OSDR somehow.

2. Funding

7

13. Provide some funding to members.
14. Increased funding to support utilization of OSDR data.
15. Funding for analyses and translational research.
16. Translational research funding from NASA.
17. NASA should either offer or engage with NSF to develop a special call for pre-doctoral research fellowships focused on using OSDR data for doctoral research.
18. Provide some more funding opportunities for analysis of plant OSDR data.
19. An internal competition of innovative projects using OSDR resources

3. Meetings and Workshops

7

1. In person meetings or retreats every now and then.
2. The [2023 ASGSR] workshop itself was a great way to encourage that for myself, now that I have been introduced to the repository at the workshop I plan on uploading all sorts of data over the next several months.
3. Specific workshops.
4. Put on hackathon with existing members.

5. One meeting each quarter just talking about OSDR data set or examples of finding and using them.
6. Workshops.
7. Maybe presentations or talks based on the interests of group members.

4. Usability/
Accessibility
6

1. Making the UI/UX even more user friendly, having small sections that describe each analysis workflow, especially the ML/AI approaches in terms of when to use, questions they answer about data and comparisons to alternative workflows.
2. Please, for the love of all things holy, include a list of acronyms and column heading definitions. Process all raw data into data tables.
3. Ensure data harmonization across projects when possible.
4. Create graphical representations of the experiments and how the data was/is generated.
5. Key strategies to encourage wider use of OSDR data could include increasing data accessibility through user-friendly interfaces.
6. Improve bugs in the platform, improve the search engine, and the visualization still never works well for me.

5. Data Generation
and Types of Analysis
4

1. Generate more GeneLab data.
2. It may be difficult, but standard multi-omics data could be collected in a central facility for best consistency... it saves effort to upload data, to input metadata etc.
3. By participation in [a] real time project.
4. Applying OSDR data to non-space experiments.

6. Training
3

1. Provide educational materials discussing the data (and related publications) for those not involved in a particular domain (such as omics or physiology).
2. Run training for clinicians.
3. Teach how to navigate the GeneLab website and gather OSDR data for beginners.

7. Publications
2

1. Organization of annual or otherwise regular special issue journal submissions of OSDR data analysis.
2. More publications using OSDR data which might incite people to look into it.

8. Software
2

1. Better software for analyze[ing] and viewing the data.
2. Better data platform.

9. Staff
1

1. The GeneLab/OSDA team is really small considering the amount and diversity data that is being collected. The community want to access the diversity of data that is now available but there are large programming hurdles preventing 'the average Jo' accessing these data. The GeneLab/OSDA team is too small to process all the data to a level where it is easily and quickly accessible, so when AWG members process these data they generate value for themselves that may not be shared and even if they want to share their analysis or for example proteomics pipeline they are not able / allowed to contribute these data or processes to the GeneLab/OSD[R] archive. So NASA is not truly utilizing the communities capacity.

10. Data Verification
and Metadata annotation
1

1. Encouraging data generators to check their OSDR submissions after they have been posted. I've come across several cases of missing data or incorrect metadata. I've usually been able to contact PIs and find the missing data but I would only know it was wrong or have access to corrections because I am very connected to the space-flight community outside of the AWG. encouraging more proofing would help with the usability of the OSDR.

11. Security
1

1. Any creative ideas, research concepts, or abstracts should be registered under the IPR Act for more liberal and open discussion. Many researchers don't want to disclose their research concepts due to unsecured mode.

General Comments

5

1. There are no suggestions and I am [a] learner and early career scientist in NASA and I am every moment learning from NASA and prepare myself to be part of NASA throughout life with my best dedication devotion with heart soul life in NASA.
2. Unique, Magnificent.
3. Ask me again after I have more involvement/exposure.
4. It was well explained on the [2023 ASGSR] meeting.
5. Accessible to all.

The last question in the survey inquired about the practices and/or resources that respondents considered as important to sustain the work of the AWGs into the future. 49 respondents provided 57 statements with their suggestions.

Figure 41. Practices and/or resources respondents consider are important to sustain the work of the AWGs into the future. 49 respondents. 57 statements.

1.
Workshops and
Community-Building
13

1. Workshop is important to bring people together.
2. Community events
3. Keep doing these workshops
4. The annual meeting/symposium should continue so that the work of all AWGs is on display and to allow for collaboration between AWGs.
5. Networking and virtual meetings
6. Meetings and learning tools
7. Yearly physical mode workshops/seminars/symposiums to enhance the interlinked & exchange of the research ideas, make a relationship between the individuals
8. Community-building which doesn't always involve laser-focus on goal for meeting.
9. I would really like to see a living element included, something like a chat function that occurs live and in real time. The comparison sounds silly, but I would love something similar to a Discord server where it would be easier to communicate, share, and collaborate with everyone rather than waiting for the meetings and coming in "unprepared".
10. Networking opportunities
11. The TOPS program should be encouraged
12. To sustain the work of AWGs into the future, it's crucial to ensure continuous fostering of a culture of interdisciplinary collaboration, and
13. Further incentives to attend... Provide some sway, once a year pay for a scientific retreat, etc

2. Funding

9

1. Increase opportunities for grant applications.
2. I am disappointed there have not been more computational-specific grants solicited by NASA Biological Physical Sciences or NASA Human Research Program. I believe there was that one plant solicitation, but the funding was extremely small to ~3 researchers to use GeneLab data. That's it. There also has been zero funding for AI/ML for all of life sciences (BPS or HRP), so this isn't surprising. I believe one grant has been awarded by BPS, and one grant by HRP, but these barely scratch the surface if space biology or space health is to be taken serious[ly*]
3. Grants namely travel
4. Funding. For developing the online presence and making it more accessible, but also making funding available to researchers to conduct ongoing research with the samples in NBiSC and the data in the repository.
5. Funding of experiments that generate data to be deposited into OSDR so that data exists.
6. More funding for data analysis and publication
7. Funding opportunities for the participants to develop collaborative proposals focused on analysis of OSDR data.
8. Grant support for attending in-person meetings and conferences, publication costs
9. Create a pool of grant opportunities

3. Data Availability and Accessibility

6

1. Increase availability of open data on a Multiomic level.
2. Accessible data, with datasets like this, if it exists, people will want to use it.
3. Standardized pipelines for analyzing data.

4. I think a true open database does not give data collectors the option to withhold raw data. I don't think it's right to give original authors decision making privilege at all-data are either public or they're not. I do understand data embargo until publication, but that should be the only autonomy the data collector should have.
5. More data in different domains, data connectivity
6. The metadata being labelled. Knowing what column names in a dataset mean is very important.

4.

Group
Dynamics

5

1. Openness, respect, curiosity and friendly productive discussions.
2. Networking and collaborations.
3. The ability for everyone to present their work and contribute their knowledge to the AWG.
4. Better integration of the different AWGs.
5. The openness of the leaders of the group helps the new researchers find suitable mentors and peers to discuss theories and results.

5.

Projects and
Publications

5

1. Have active projects that can/will lead to publications.
2. Continuous Literature Review: Regularly monitoring the latest research and developments in space-related fields, such as astrobiology, microgravity research, and space medicine, is crucial. This ensures that AWGs stay up to date with the most current knowledge and can adapt their projects and priorities accordingly. Regarding the specific resource mentioned, "www.spacebio.space," it can indeed be a valuable asset for Genelab and other AWGs. Websites and databases dedicated to space-related information can serve as centralized hubs for data, research papers, and other resources.
6. Impactful papers
7. Collaboration and contributions from interested members for undertaking a project ultimately resulting in a co-authored publication or grant.
8. Support publications.

6.

Outreach and Education

4

1. Outreach.
2. Education is an important element. Online tutorials, workshops and webinars can enable one to acquire new skills, practice and then use it with the OSDR data. AI/ML Education Project by James and Lauren is a great example to this.
3. Involvement of students (undergraduate level)
4. Tutorials

7.

Data Analysis capabilities

4

1. Enable within site data analysis options.
2. As we get more data, getting access to collaborators who have the compute power to process the large quantity of data.
3. Computational power
4. Embrace cutting-edge technologies and data analytics tools.

8.

Career development support

3

1. Career path indication in open science, recognition of contribution leading to job, funding etc. (under current scientific culture, evaluation system)
2. Internships are a helpful way to support the career development of early career academics, even if remote, unpaid and performed within academic programmes.
3. Invest in training and mentorship programs for emerging scientists.

9.
Ethics
2

1. Protection of the rights of those who generate the data that is deposited into OSDR so that data continues to be generated.
2. Ethical peer review of practices. Transparency of funding sources and resources being used to utilize genelab. To harvest output for individuals.

10.
Staff
1

1. GeneLab/OSDA [OSDR] needs more programmers and bioinformaticians to build tools to allow the community to access more diverse types of data. There are so many different ways these data can aggregated and viewed that it is overwhelming for most AWG visitors. For example, most AWG community members don't have the skills or finance to setup software that can pull images from the OSDA and then allow segmentation &/or other types of analysis using modern tools like GTP to create natural language questions that can be answered by these data. The same is true for the molecular data. If GeneLab/OSD [OSDR] had a larger team they could create more user friendly software, lowering the bar to use these new methods, increasing access to modern analysis techniques as well the primary data.

Expand
applications
1

1. Applying the space related research to earth based studies so everyone can contribute and feels like the space biology question is applicable to advancing Earth studies.

12.
Continuous
assessment
1

1. This is something that should be continued to be assessed every 6 months or so. I feel like the AWG is building traction and growing so it may be too early to say but keeping the momentum and firmly stating the goals for each group to work towards each year is important too.

13.
General
Comments
3

1. Everything is one word infinity useful
2. Everyday learning and creative thinking in NASA
3. Open source data

The variety of perspectives across all these statements and the themes they cover show overall praise about the repository, the groups' inclusive and friendly environment, the opportunities for collaboration, and the benefits of participation in the groups for professional development. Regarding negative aspects, some respondents brought up issues of leadership styles and direction of the groups. Finally, when it came to suggested courses of action, respondents had different levels of familiarity with the repository's already existing policies and practices regarding consultation of subject matter experts, and the fact that AWG members cannot claim affiliation with NASA. The implementation of the online Discourse 'forum space' in May, 2024 with the support of the Blue Marble Space Institute of Science (BMSIS) marked a significant development allowing AWG members to interact with each other and visualize existing projects and opportunities in one place. Unfortunately, the implementation of this space began shortly after the closing of the survey and the survey was not able to capture its impact on the interactions amongst AWG members. Thus, the suggestion to introduce more dynamic, real-time collaboration tools to facilitate immediate communication has already been implemented by the program. Statements about maintaining active projects that lead to publications highlight that indeed publications are and will continue to be key outcomes from the collaborative efforts in the AWGs. Regarding institutional resources, workshops and community-building activities alongside funding were the most salient issues. Many responses emphasized the importance of fostering collaboration and networking among AWG members highlighting the role of workshops and in-person meetings. Regarding funding, some courses of action were suggested, and there were calls for computational-specific grant solicitations, travel grants, and grants for data analysis and publication.

One response pointed to the limited availability of grants from NASA's Biological Physical Sciences (BPS) and the Human Research Program (HRP). These opportunities were perceived as insufficient for space biology and health. Funding limitations evidently also limit the number of experiments that generate data for repositories like OSDR. Moreover, scientific retreats and spaces for networking and community building are ways for AWG members to stay engaged. Some respondents consider that funding these activities would help sustain ongoing research and collaboration.

Outreach and education initiatives were also recognized by respondents as important for equipping researchers with the necessary skills to work with the complex data produced by space biology experiments. The AI/ML Education Project was mentioned as a successful example of a program that could be expanded. Online tutorials, workshops, and webinars continue to be a key part of OSDR's effort to broaden participation. In October 2024, after the closing of the survey, the OSDR team released updated and new tutorials to use and navigate the various features and tools in the repository.

Conclusions and Recommendations

From its conception in 2014, GeneLab aimed to develop “an integrated repository and bioinformatics data system for analysis and modeling;” to engage “the broadest possible community of researchers, industry, and the general public to foster innovation;” and to strengthen “international partnerships by leveraging existing capabilities and data sharing” (GeneLab Strategic Plan 2014, 1). Over one decade later and integrated into OSDR, the findings of this survey substantiate the fact that the program has had a very positive impact in all those fronts. In particular, the program has contributed to turning the space biology scientific community into a more international and diverse network of scientists.

The finding about the expansion of the community poses the challenge of continuing the characterization started by this survey, and sustaining the growth of the community in size, diversity of technical expertise, and lived experience. It has been identified that research communities that support NASA science missions are constantly gaining and losing researchers (NASEM 2022, 55). According to the *Foundations* report, it is “both a task and a challenge” to determine if losses are occurring for reasons such as “lack of opportunities, discrimination, or lack of an inclusive climate, so that these causal factors can be addressed” (NASEM 2022, 56). Next to these concerns that apply to all SMD, space biology poses some specific challenges regarding career stages considering the shifting priorities in the field regarding exploration destinations, limited funding opportunities, the operational constraints of the experimental program, and flight delays during key moments in early career researchers. Some senior researchers in interviews have expressed their concerns with retaining the expertise of the younger researchers they have trained.

The combination of expertise between PIs and members of teams that have conducted spaceflight experiments and those joining the AWGs from other areas of expertise has proven fruitful regarding publication campaigns and individual papers. However, more work is needed to track these collaborations into grant applications, new experimental designs, and the permanence of new researchers in the field. The pertinence of the respondents’ scientific interests and skills for the scientific priorities defined by the 2023 *Decadal Survey* could be emphasized by the program as a route to provide more guided training and funding opportunities for data reanalysis and new experiments.

Acknowledging the persistent challenges posed by funding constraints, there are alternative approaches that are less focused on resources to recognize the contributions made by AWG members. The OSDR (formerly GeneLab) Chats on YouTube have effectively showcased researchers when they publish key papers resulting from their work in the AWGs. Along these lines there could be other modes of recognition implemented by the program that focus on other dimensions of the collaborative nature of the AWGs

work. In studies of open science practices in other domains, it has been noted that “without formal credit for outputs beyond papers, researchers struggle to negotiate what counts as, and how to be open with, intellectual contributions” (Levin and Leonelli 2017, 283).

The finding about the diverse and mostly positive experiences of participation calls for the development of new metrics to assess aspects of the groups' other than publications. The program has appropriately emphasized that the AWGs have increased the knowledge generated per experiment, particularly in terms of return on investment in the realm of publications. However, what counts as 'productivity' in the groups goes beyond publications and there are other dimensions of AWG members' interactions and work not currently reflected in those figures.

One way to achieve the goal of continuous monitoring of those other dimensions is to develop processes in which indicators of participation are embedded. The 'forum space' implemented in May 2024 after the closing of this survey has been a remarkable step as a communications platform bringing the AWG community together and giving more visibility to projects and opportunities. The OSDR team has started to incorporate usage data of this space as part of their indicators when presenting the work of the AWGs to diverse audiences. One recommendation is to embed a subset of the questions posed by this survey in this space to generate more robust and continuous data. Additionally, acknowledging the fact that the groups have a great degree of autonomy in their functioning, proposing some consistent categories across the groups to track aspects of members' participation during meetings and ongoing projects is advisable.

Finally, one overall recommendation is to make the infrastructural work of the repository and its staff more visible for the AWG community. The AWGs are sustained by policy, computational, and human infrastructures that are sometimes taken for granted or, at best, are opaque to many participants in the groups as revealed by some answers that suggested courses of action that were already in place or were institutionally not possible. Since 2022, NASA has taken significant steps with the policy frameworks and institutional setups for open science, and the repository has unique expertise amongst the team of curators, bioinformaticians, and communications team. One way to make this work visible and to produce metrics that grasp key dimensions of OSDR is to embed a process graph in the datasets that tracks the labor involved in curating it and making them available. Finding ways to make the infrastructural work visible for users is also a way to foster their involvement with the repository and to acknowledge their feedback with pipelines, metadata standards, and other aspects of the data systems.

As data-centric space biology aims to move towards more automated methods that will increase precision in some ways but not in all, the ever-imperfect science of humans coming together to produce knowledge will continue to be relevant. In sum, maximizing discovery is democratizing access, and the long-term goal of increasing integration across different types of data within and across species, enabling AI-readiness of that data, and generating new data in spaceflight and ground experiments will require sustaining the collaborative work of the network of experts in the AWGs.

References

- Berrios, Daniel C, Jonathan Galazka, Kirill Grigorev, Samrawit Gebre, and Sylvain V Costes (2021). "NASA GeneLab: Interfaces for the Exploration of Space Omics Data." *Nucleic Acids Research* 49(D1), D1515–22. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa887>
- Castaño, Paola (2023). "Plant Biologists and the International Space Station: Institutionalising a Scientific Community" in Salazar, Juan Francisco, and Alice Gorman. *The Routledge Handbook of Social Studies of Outer Space*. Routledge Anthropology Handbooks. Abingdon New York: Routledge, 427-440.
- Cell (2020). *Biology of Spaceflight Collection*. <https://www.cell.com/c/the-biology-of-spaceflight>
- Costes, Sylvain V., Chelle Gentemann, Steven Platts, and Lisa Carnell (2024). "Biological Horizons: Pioneering Open Science in the Cosmos." *Nature Communications* 15(1), 4780. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-48633-2>
- Foust, Jeff (2025). "NASA shuts diversity offices to comply with executive order". *Space News*. <https://spacenews.com/nasa-shutters-diversity-offices-to-comply-with-executive-order/>
- GeneLab (2014). *Strategic Plan*. NASA Space Biosciences Technical Reports. <https://www.nasa.gov/ames/space-biosciences/space-biosciences-technical-report/>
- GeneLab (2022). Open Science for Life in Space. <https://www.nasa.gov/osdr-genelab-about/>
- Gentemann, Chelle. (2023). "Why NASA and Federal Agencies Are Declaring This the Year of Open Science." *Nature* 613, no. 7943: 217 <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-00019-y>
- Holdren, John P. (2013). *Memorandum for the heads of executive departments and agencies: Increasing access to the results of federally funded scientific research*. Office of Science and Technology Policy. https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/sites/default/files/microsites/ostp/ostp_public_access_memo_2013.pdf
- Levin, Nadine and Sabina Leonelli (2017). "How Does One "Open" Science? Questions of Value in Biological Research." *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 42 (2), 280-305. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243916672071>
- Leonelli, Sabina (2023). *Philosophy of Open Science*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009416368>
- NASA OSDR, Analysis Working Groups Charter. (2025). <https://www.nasa.gov/osdr-working-groups-awg-charter/>

- NASA (2022). *NASA Strategic Plan for Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, & Accessibility* https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/nasa_deia_strategic_plan-fy22-fy26-final_tagged.pdf (NASA Website unavailable in February, 2025). The document has been archived here: https://web.archive.org/web/20241128073245/https://nodis3.gsfc.nasa.gov/OPD_Docs/NPS_1001_106_.pdf
- NASA (2024). *National Aeronautics and Space Administration Policy Statement on Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Accessibility for NASA's Workforce and Workplaces*. Document NPS 3713.101. https://nodis3.gsfc.nasa.gov/OPD_docs/NPS_3713_101_.pdf (NASA Website unavailable in February, 2025). The document has been archived here: <https://spacegrant.arizona.edu/sites/spacegrant.arizona.edu/files/NASA-DEIA-Policy-2024.pdf>
- NASA (2025). Amendment 109: Removing DEIA Requirements from ROSES-2024. <https://science.nasa.gov/researchers/solicitations/roses-2024/amendment-109-removing-deia-requirements-from-roses-2024/>
- NASA Science Mission Directorate (2022). *Scientific Information Policy for the Science Mission Directorate SMD Policy Document SPD-41a*. <https://science.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/smd-information-policy-spd-41a.pdf>
- NASEM, National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2022). *Foundations of a Healthy and Vital Research Community for NASA Science*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/26575>
- NASEM, National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (2023). *Thriving in Space: Ensuring the Future of Biological and Physical Sciences Research: A Decadal Survey for 2023-2032*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/26750>
- Nature Portfolio (2024). *Space Omics and Medical Atlas (SOMA) across orbits*. <https://www.nature.com/immersive/d42859-024-00009-8/index.html>.
- NCSES, National Center for Science and Engineering Statistics (2023). *Diversity and STEM: Women, Minorities, and Persons with Disabilities 2023*. Special Report NSF 23-315. Alexandria, VA: National Science Foundation <https://nces.nsf.gov/wmpd>.
- Nelson, Alondra (2022). *Memorandum for the heads of executive departments and agencies: Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research*. Office of Science and Technology Policy <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/08-2022-OSTP-Public-access-Memo.pdf>
- Ray, Shayoni, Samrawit Gebre, Homer Fogle, Daniel C Berrios, Peter B Tran, Jonathan M Galazka, and Sylvain V Costes (2019). "GeneLab: Omics Database for Spaceflight Experiments." *Bioinformatics* 35, no. 10: 1753–59. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty884>
- Sanders, Lauren, Danielle Lopez, Alan Wood, Ryan Scott, Samrawit Gebre, Amanda Saravia-Butler, and Sylvain V Costes (2024). "Celebrating 30 Years of Access to NASA Space Life Sciences Data." *GigaScience* 13 <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/giae066>

Appendix: Survey Questions

Qualtrics

NASA OSDR Analysis Working Groups Survey

Introduction

NASA's Open Science Data Repository (OSDR) Analysis Working Groups (AWGs) have brought together a large network of people and represent a unique and significant experience for space biology and open science. This survey aims to characterize the AWGs' members, their expertise, and experience participating in the groups. This characterization is important for OSDR to learn about the groups' work, for NASA's move towards open science, and for global studies about good practices in open science.

The project Philosophy of Open Science of Diverse Research Environments (PHIL_OS) is conducting a multi-year study of GeneLab as part of OSDR, and this survey is a key instrument in that study. The PHIL_OS project combines empirical research and philosophical analysis on how diverse research environments enact and conceptualize open science. The project is based at the Exeter Centre for the Study of the Life Sciences (Egenis) at the University of Exeter. The principal investigator is Prof. Sabina Leonelli (s.leonelli@exeter.ac.uk) and the lead of this case study is Dr. Paola Castaño (pac223@exeter.ac.uk). This project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. The researchers have no conflicts of interest relating to the subject matter, the individuals, or the institutions involved in the research. You can find more information about the PHIL_OS project here: <https://opensciencestudies.eu>.

Informed Consent

You have been invited to contribute to this survey because you currently participate or have participated in NASA's OSDR Analysis Working Groups and are over 18 years of age. Participation is entirely voluntary, and participants will not receive payment for taking part. You will be asked questions about yourself and your experience with the OSDR AWGs. We will not ask for your name or email address, and all information will be received, used, and reported in anonymous form, with the aim to make direct identification of yourself impossible. You can discontinue participation in the survey at any time for any reason without any consequences to you.

The results of this survey will be available in academic publications and reports, and we are committed to sharing the results with the OSDR community in workshops and meetings. For other outputs, a regularly updated list of publications can be found on the project website <https://opensciencestudies.eu>, and you may request a copy of all relevant publications from the project team. If you wish to receive regular email updates about the project, please sign up to our mailing list contact@opensciencestudies.org. The PHIL_OS project and this survey have been reviewed and approved by the Faculty of Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences Research Ethics Committee at the University of Exeter. For further information about the research, please contact Sabina Leonelli or Paola Castaño. If you have concerns/questions about the research ethics you would like to discuss with someone else at the University, please contact the Faculty of Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences Research Ethics Committee fhass-ethics@exeter.ac.uk.

We appreciate your time in filling out this survey! Estimated time: 5-10 minutes.

* In all open required questions, feel free to write "I prefer not to say" if that is your preferred response.

A. Please confirm that you have read and understood the above information

- Yes
- I am not sure. We welcome the opportunity to resolve any queries you may have so you can complete the informed consent process and participate in the survey. Please let us know your question or questions and whether you are willing to discuss them via email contacting Dr. Paola Castaño pac223@exeter.ac.uk. If you have concerns or questions that you would like to discuss with someone else at the University of Exeter, please contact the Faculty of Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences Research Ethics Committee fhass-ethics@exeter.ac.uk.

B. Do you agree to take part in the above project by filling out this survey?

- Yes
- No

1. What are the academic disciplines or fields in which you conduct most of your work? _____

2. Are you employed by NASA as a civil servant or contractor?

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to say

3. Are you employed by NASA's OSDR?

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to say

4. In which sector do you work?

- Academia
- Government

- Industry
- Learned society, National Academy, or professional body Non-profit organization
- I prefer not to say
- Another sector

5. If you work in academia, which of the following categories best describes your career status?

- Undergraduate student
- Master's student
- PhD student
- Postdoctoral researcher
- Assistant professor
- Associate professor
- Professor
- Researcher
- Instructional staff
- Laboratory technician
- I prefer not to say
- Other career status _____

6. What space biology question most interests you? _____

7. What fundamental biology question most interests you? _____

8. Are you or have you been part of a team that has designed and flown (or is already approved to fly) a spaceflight experiment?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know
- prefer not to say

9. Please mention up to three of your technical skills? (For example, programming, statistical analysis, RNAseq analysis, etc) _____

10. Please indicate in which professional associations you are a member, if any (For example, American Society of Gravitational and Space Research, American Society of Plant Biologists, etc) _____

11. In which AWG or AWGs do you participate? (Please select all that apply)

- AI/ML
- ALSDA
- Animals
- Microbes
- Multi-omics
- Plants
- I prefer not to say

12. Approximately, when did you first join the AWG or AWGs in which you participate? (If you participate in more than one AWG, please indicate the date for each)_____

13. Considering an average week in the last month (or less if you have joined more recently), how many hours per week did you spend on AWG-related work?

- Less than 2 hours
- 2 - 8 hours
- More than 8 hours
- I do not know
- I prefer not to say

14. Have you deposited your data into NASA's OSDR (GeneLab, ALSDA, NBISC, BSP)?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know
- I prefer not to say

15. Have you used open databases other than NASA's OSDR?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know
- I prefer not to say

16. Have you worked as a paid staff member or as a volunteer in an open database other than NASA's OSDR?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know
- I prefer not to say

17. Have you deposited data into an open database other than NASA's OSDR?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know
- I prefer not to say

18. What are your top three motivations to participate in the AWGs? (Please rank the options by dragging them up or down to the positions in which you want them. We will only consider the first three as part of your response).

- 1 - Answering fundamental space biology questions
- 2 - Answering applied space biology questions
- 3 - Publishing for professional advancement
- 4 - Collaborating to design new spaceflight experiments
- 5 - Staying updated with NASA space biology

- 6 - Acquiring skills about data analysis for research
- 7- Learning about data available through NASA's OSDR
- 8- Networking for career development
- 9- Other _____

19. Have you been a co-author in any peer-reviewed publication (accepted for publication or already published) resulting from work in your AWG or AWGs?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know
- I prefer not to say

20. If your answer was "yes" in the previous question, please indicate in which role or roles you participated (Please select all that apply)

- Conception and design
- Data curation
- Data analysis
- Data visualization
- Writing - original draft
- Writing - reviewing and editing
- Project administration
- Funding acquisition
- I do not know
- I prefer not to say
- Other _____

21. In which of the following activities have you collaborated with members of your AWG or AWGs (Please select all that apply)

- Grant applications to conduct a spaceflight experiment
- Feedback on their work
- Policy-facing activities
- Educational activities
- Decadal survey topical white paper
- Decadal survey research campaign white paper
- All of the above
- None of the above
- I do not know
- I prefer not to say
- Other

22. Considering the main AWG in which you participate, please evaluate the performance of the group in these aspects:

	Poor	Satisfactory	Good	I do not know	I prefer not to say	Not applicable
Integrating expertise from different disciplines	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Gaining new insights from existing data	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Seeking support from OS DR with specific datasets or technical concerns	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Keeping a core membership	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Involving students	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Developing new methods	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Developing new models	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Publishing papers re- analyzing OS DR data	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Designing new experiments	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Writing grant proposals	<input type="checkbox"/>					

23. How closely would you say the metadata from OS DR characterizes the experiments?

- Not closely
- Somewhat closely
- Very closely
- I do not know
- I prefer not to say

24. What is your gender identity?

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- I prefer not to say
- My gender is best described as _____

25. What is your age group?

- 18-24
- 25-34

- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65-74
- 75+
- I prefer not to say

26. What is your ethnicity? (The categories below are broadly based on those used in census data from the United States and United Kingdom, and we acknowledge that they do not apply internationally. So, please feel free to add the ethnic category that best suits you and the specifications you consider represent your ethnicity in the categories below)

- Black or from African origin _____
- East Asian or from East Asian origin _____
- Hispanic or Latino _____
- Middle Eastern from Middle Eastern origin _____
- Mixed or multiethnic _____
- Native American _____
- Native Hawaiian _____
- Pacific Islander _____
- South Asian or from South Asian origin _____
- South East Asian or from South East Asian origin _____
- White _____
- I do not know
- I prefer not to say
- My ethnicity is best described as _____

27. In which country do you work? _____

Finally, based on your experience participating in the AWGs, we would very much appreciate your thoughts on these last three questions.

28. Do you have any other considerations you would like to share about positive and/or negative aspects of your experience participating in the AWGs? _____

29. What strategies would you suggest to encourage broader involvement in utilization of OSDR data? _____

30. What practices and/or resources do you consider are important to sustain the work of the AWGs into the future? _____
